

Managing potato blackleg: why it still matters

Over the past five years, viruses have been at the forefront of potato seed downgrades. However, blackleg and soft rot causing pathogens remain an issue. Downgrades for blackleg still occur and roguing out blackleg plants remains a significant cost for growers.

Blackleg still poses a considerable threat to the potato industry as outbreaks are likely to occur in years/regions with conditions that favour disease development.

Image credit: Kyran Maloney (SAC)

Image credit: Ashleigh Holmes (Hutton)

What is blackleg?

Blackleg is a bacterial disease that causes non-emergence and stunting in the field leading to the downgrading or rejection of seed, ware and processing crops. Infection typically originates from the mother tuber causing black lesions at the base of the potato stem, near the soil line, with pale green to yellow wilting of upper leaves.

Aerial stem rot causes brown/black lesions that appear higher up the plant stem, resulting from bacterial infections through wounds (e.g. from wind or insect feeding).

Blackleg pathogens can survive and persist on the tuber surface, lenticels and stolon ends, causing soft rot losses of tubers in the field and in store under favourable conditions (temp >4°C, high humidity).

SASA © Crown Copyright

Image credit: Greig Cahill (SASA)

What causes blackleg and soft rot?

- The disease is caused by *Pectobacterium* or *Dickeya* species of bacteria. Currently, up to 95% of blackleg in Scotland is attributed to *Pectobacterium atrosepticum*, with the remaining cases attributed to *P. parmentieri* and, to a lesser extent, *P. brasiliense*. Scottish seed potatoes are free from blackleg caused by *Dickeya* spp.
- *P. atrosepticum* is likely to be the main pathogen in England.
- Across Europe, the main cause of blackleg is *P. brasiliense*, supported by recent surveys in the Netherlands. Limited amounts of disease are caused by *P. parmentieri*, *D. dianthicola*, and *D. solani*.
- Many strains previously known as *P. carotovorum* are being renamed as new/different species based on new genome sequencing methods. Research continues to better understand the economic importance and distribution of these species in Great Britain.
- Although not responsible for large scale losses, other species known to infect potatoes include *P. maceratum*, *P. parvum*, *P. peruviense*, *P. polaris*, *P. punjabense*, and *P. versatile*.

Authors:

Ashleigh Holmes,
Sonia Humphris
(James Hutton Institute)
Greig Cahill (SASA)
Kyran Maloney
(SAC Consulting)
Joana Vicente (Fera)

Sources of infection

- The first field generation of high grade seed can become contaminated through wind or rain dispersed aerosols from neighbouring infected potato crops, insects, surface water, soil, groundwater, and contaminated machinery.
- Bacteria can infect growing plants from the mother tuber via the stolon or wounds.
- Bacteria can survive on the tuber surface and in lenticels, contaminating progeny seed tubers used for subsequent field generations. This can lead to cross-contamination of clean seed in stores, particularly where conditions promote soft rot development (condensation and >4°C).
- Bacterial loads on tubers typically increase after each field generation.

Management

- Currently, there are no available treatments to directly control blackleg on seed or in the field. New methods of biocontrol, such as the use of bacteriophages, are under investigation.
- All potato varieties are susceptible to blackleg and soft rot to varying degrees. There is no known host resistance to deploy.
- Planting high grade seed can reduce the incidence of blackleg in the field.
- Irrigation management and good field drainage can restrict blackleg development as wet conditions, through rainfall or overirrigation, promotes disease and tuber infestation.
- Rapid haulm destruction and desiccation reduce bacterial spread and tuber contamination. During storage, strict temperature control (4°C) and dry air ventilation is essential to prevent conditions optimal for bacteria multiplication and soft rot development.